

THE ENGLISH ADAPTATION LEVEL OF BSED-ENGLISH CALL CENTER AGENTS

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The English Adaptation Level of BSED-English Call Center Agents

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Abstract

English speaking is the language of business globally, therefore, having a high level of English will open doors to more job opportunities and making an attractive employee to companies. The study aimed to find out the English adaptation of Bachelor of Secondary Education English major graduates at Davao City Call Centers. Specifically, the study sought to determine the following sub-problems which are the level of English Proficiency level of BSED-English Graduates before they become call center agents in terms of grammar, sentence mastery, vocabulary, pronunciation, and fluency; the English Proficiency level of BSED-English Graduates during their employment as call center agents in terms of grammar, sentence mastery, vocabulary, pronunciation, and fluency; the significant differences in the mean scores of each of the five (5) English Proficiency parameters before and during employment of the BSED-English graduates as call center agents. An English Proficiency Test and TOEFL test for teacher were utilized as the research instrument in the gathering data which contain items adapted and modified from various English proficiency test and TOEFL test for teachers' which suit to the level of the teachers. Test of English as a Foreign Language known as TOEFL test is a standardized test to measure the English Language ability of non-native speakers to evaluate the English speaking and understanding ability of a speaker. Based on the data gathered and analyzed, the . The findings showed that before the employment of the BSE-English as call center agents their English proficiency level in grammar was good as revealed by the mean score of 11.80, in sentence mastery their English proficiency level was also good as indicated by the mean score of 11.80. moreover, in vocabulary their English proficiency level was also good as justified by the mean score of 11.20, in pronunciation their English proficiency level is very good as proven by the mean score of 4.93, and in fluency their proficiency level was also very good as stated by the mean score of 4.53. Moreover, during the employment of the BSED-English graduates as call center agents their English proficiency levels in the following language areas are the following; in grammar their proficiency level is very good as revealed by the mean score of 13.25, in sentence mastery their proficiency level is also very good as justified by the score of 12.80 in vocabulary their proficiency level is also very good with the mean score of 13.40, in pronunciation their proficiency level is also very good with the mean score of 5.46, and in fluency their proficiency level is also very good as proven by the mean score of 5.40. In the study, the results show that there are significant differences between the students' English proficiency before and during their employment as call center agents: in grammar the computed t-value is 4.460. In sentence mastery the computed t-value is 4.365, in vocabulary the computed t-value is 5.662, in pronunciation the computed t-value is 5.112, and in fluency the computed t-value is 4.203 which are all higher than the tabular t-value of $\neq 2.145$. The study was concluded that the employment of BSED-English graduate to call centers has positively contributed to the English adaptation of the respondents. Further, it is concluded that the employment of respondents to the call centers has improved their English proficiency level in grammar, vocabulary, sentence mastery, pronunciation and fluency.

Keywords: *adaptation, language, students, proficiency*

Introduction

English Language Proficiency is the ability to speak or perform an acquainted language. As theories vary among pedagogies as to what constitutes language adaptations go, there is a little consistency as to how agents adapt it. It aims for the development of the basic skills such as listening and speaking. Proficiency in oral and written English and flexibility in dealing with foreign cultures remain the key advantages of Filipino contact center agents over those of other countries in Asia – including China.

Additionally, fluency and language competence are generally recognized as being related, but separate controversial subjects. In predominant frameworks, proficient speakers demonstrate both accuracy and fluency, and use a variety of discourse strategies. Thus the native speakers of a language can be fluent without being considered proficient.

Oral Proficiency Interview is a standardized, global assessment of functional speaking ability. Taking the form of conversation between the tester and test taker, the test measures how well a person speaks a language by assessing their performance of a range of language tasks against specific criteria.

There are many scholars who have made great achievements in many aspects. In spite of their achievements, the present studies are mostly limited to applying the language adaptation theory explaining foreign language from a macro perspective and lack the speaking practice.

Nowadays, call centers are widespread in the Philippine territory, and these offer job opportunities to many Filipinos who can communicate in English. The employment of workers to call centers provides them opportunities to converse with native English

speakers frequently. This situation trains the call center agents to speak the English language with ease and precision that eventually help them adapt the correct English Accent that aid them speak the English Language Spontaneously.

According to Verschueren (1987) language use is a kind of behavior which requires practice to achieve accuracy of rules and correct production of its sounds. In the area where the study will be conducted, it is observed that the BSEd-English graduates who work as call center agent have tremendously improved their speaking skills due to frequent conversation to the native English speakers on the phone.

To validate this observation, the researchers will conduct a study on the Oral English Adaptation to the English Proficiency of the BSEd-English graduates. It is in this premise the study is deemed important.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out the English Adaptation Level of BSEd-English Graduates as Call Center Agents. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the English Proficiency Level of BSEd-English Graduates before they become call center agents in terms of;
 - 1.1. Grammar;
 - 1.2. Sentence Mastery;
 - 1.3. Vocabulary;
 - 1.4. Pronunciation; and
 - 1.5. Fluency?
2. What is the English Proficiency Level of BSEd-English Graduates during their employment as call center agents in terms of;
 - 2.1. Grammar;
 - 2.2. Sentence Mastery;
 - 2.3. Vocabulary;
 - 2.4. Pronunciation; and
 - 2.5. Fluency?
3. Are there any significant differences in the mean scores of each of the five (5) English Proficiency parameters before and during employment of the BSEd-English graduates as call center agents?
4. Based on the findings, what instructional materials will be compiled to enhance the learner's level of English proficiency.

Literature Review

History of Call Centers in Philippines

The BPO industry in the Philippines started from a single contact center, the Accenture Global Resource Center, which was founded by Frank Holz in 1992. The Philippine Economic Zone Authority was established in 1995. This act provided lower area requirements for developments and tax incentives, which consequently attracted foreign investors. The Convergys Corporation opened up two more call centers in the Philippines. It was the time when Jack Frecker, the president of Convergys Corporation, announced the incorporation of the Philippines in the revenue generation plan and the global expansion of the company. In 2005, accounting for 2.4% of the country's GDP, the Philippine acquired over 3% of the Global BPO market. A year after, with PLDTVentures leading in the BPO industry, domestic economy increased by 5.4% and 11,000 more people were employed. In 2010, the Philippines were then declared the world's BPO capital. From this point, the BPO industry continued to grow and generate more revenue, with the industry providing the most job opportunities in the private sector (https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_process_outsourcing_in_the_Philippines)

Call centers began in the Philippines as providers of email response and managing services then broadened to industrial capabilities for almost all types of customer relations, ranging from travel services, technical support, education, customer care, financial services, online business-to-customer support, and online business-to-business support. The call center industry is one of the fastest growing in the country.

The Philippines is also considered a location of choice due to its less expensive operational and labor costs, and a constant stream of college-educated graduates entering the already mostly young workforce. The Filipino people also generally show proficiency in American-style English as well as slang, and strong familiarity with U>S and European cultures (https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Call_center_industry_in_the_Philippines).

BPO in the Philippines

The Philippine Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) defines BPO as the "delegation of service-type business processed to a third party service provider". BPO in the Philippines is becoming a key developing industry.

Primarily due to the relatively low cost of living, and a workplace which composed mainly of young and educated Filipinos with good spoken English language skills (<https://www.aseanbriefing.com/news/2017/04/17/business-outsourcing-philippines.html>).

According to Del Prado Lee, et. Al (2015), Philippines has established itself a top destination for BPO services, in particular for contact

service, in endowment in human capital-more than a quarter of the population holds a tertiary degree, and more than half a million graduates from college each year, most with both an excellent command of the English language and cultural affinity. Consequently, Philippines has also managed to develop a competitive advantage in voice-based BPO services

Furthermore, Lee, et.al (2014), states the delegation of telecommunications industry in 1993, the Philippines has developed globally competitive ICT infrastructure, with two fibre-optic networks covering most regions of the country.

Tracing the growth in the BPO industry in the Philippines can provide a broader context. The industry has undergone three phases i-in the 1990's when the first BPO operations were established, most of them contract center; ii- during the early 2000s there was a transition towards higher value added activities such as transcription services and back-office in accounting and finance; and iii- medical transcription (<http://www.rappler.com/business/industries/215-tech-biz/83186-ph-climbs-cloud-readiness-index>).

Communication in Foreign Language-Survey

An international world today needs ability to communicate in English. The national syllabus of English in the Swedish compulsory school clearly emphasizes throughout the world. The ability to use English for studies, travel and for social, professional and international contracts of different transactions (the Swedish National Agency for Education [www.]).

Kalmar's study states that in 1940's and 1950's a structuralist view among linguists was dominant. The structuralist linguists described languages and different components of a language were scientifically identified. The structural school only investigated the evident data. Things like consciousness and intuition were not observable areas.

The scientist Skinner and other behaviorists viewed language as behavior and saw it as verbal habits which have been acquired by the speaker through imitations and rewards (Littlewood 1992).

Newmark (1966) points out the problem of foreign language learners who have the ability to produce grammatically correct sentences but who are unable to communicate correctly in the target language.

Chomsky (1960) claimed that it was not only to describe the languages through outer stimulus and response. He argued that the linguistics needed to add an explanatory level in their description of language. Chomsky claimed that language learning is genetically conditions and all humans are born with a native ability to acquire a language and that language develops automatically with when people are exposed to the surroundings (Ericson 1993).

Furthermore, Brown (2000) explained the social constructivist perspective that are associated with more current approaches to both first and language acquisition emphasize the dynamic nature of the interplay between learners and their peers and others with whom they interact. The interpersonal context in which a learner operates takes a great significance, and therefore, the interaction between learners and others is the focus of observation and explanation (Brown 2000).

Definition of Language Learning Strategies

Language learning strategies are used by learners to complete speaking, reading, vocabulary, listening or writing activities presented in language lessons. Recognizing that there is a task to complete or a problem to solve language learners will use whatever metacognitive, cognitive or social effective strategies they possess to attend to the language learning activity (Oxford, 1990). However, novices may be less efficient at selecting and applying strategies task (O'Malley & Chamot).

Weinstein and Mayer (1994) defined learning strategies broadly as "behavior of a learner engages in during learning which are intended to influence the learner's encoding process". Later Mayer (1998) defined learning strategies as "behavior of a learner that are intended to influence how the learner processes information". These early definitions from the educational literature reflect the roots of learning strategies in cognitive science, with its essential assumptions that human beings process information and that learning involves such information processing.

Research by Robbins (1996) and Grunewald (1999) also provide insights into instructional sequences and teaching approaches. The research discovered the feasibility of learning strategies instruction in Japan. Robbins (1996) provides a qualitative description of the instructional sequences used to implement strategy instruction, Robbins used the problem solving process model.

Multiple Meaning and Definitions of Grammar

Grammar is a central to the organization of language and meaning. Knowledge of grammar allows us to analyze and describe the ways in which words are selected, organized and sequenced within a text to make meaning.

Chomsky argues that the human brain contains a limited set of constraints for organizing language. This implies in turn that all languages have a common structural basis: the set of rules known as "universal grammar".

Speakers are proficient in a language know which expressions are acceptable in their language and which are unacceptable. The key puzzle is how speakers come to know these restrictions of their language, since expressions that violate those restrictions are not present in the input, indicated as such. Chomsky argued that this poverty of stimulus means that Skinner's behaviourist perspective cannot explain language acquisition. The absence of negative evidence – evidence that an expression is part of a class of ungrammatical

sentences given language is the score of his argument.

Patrick Hartwell (1985), published an article define the meaning of grammar, “Grammar, Grammars, and the Teaching of Grammar” appeared in College English and has enjoyed a number of reprints. Anyone who has encountered this piece might imagine that, to define the meaning of grammar. Hartwell’s footsteps, covering the same ground, and reporting his research verbatim. However, Hartwell attempts to cover far too much territory in his article, as he move quickly from definitions- omitting at least one important example, usage, since he assumes his readers are familiar with it.

The Webster’s Third New International Dictionary (1986) lists the branch of linguistic study that deals with the classes of words, their inflections or other means of indicating relation to each other, and their functions and sentence.

Mustafa Albay (2017) states Wilcox (2004) definition of grammar as “a system of rules which allows the users of the language in question to create meaning, by building both meaningful words and larger constructions of sentences”. Grammar involves a set of rules that enables language learners to understand a language and produce accurate expressions. Grammar teaching allows learners to recognize target linguistic features. Language learners need to know these features work in sentences in order to use the language accurately. It goes without saying that the effective use of a language with a great capability highly depends on understanding of it grammar.

Carolyn (1998) argues that before the learners engage in speaking comprehension of spoken language must be developed. This method was based on the idea that speaking in the target language emerge naturally hence there is no point in forcing them to speak before they are ready. The learners are expected to understand the grammar rules naturally without explanations, the way grammar is taught in total physical response has been questioned.

Balabagan (2015) states Saddler (2008), one area of writing that may be particularly problematic for less skilled writers and language learners is constructing well-formed sentences.

Chin (2000) states, grammar is the sound, structure, and meaning system of language. All languages have grammar, and each language has its own grammar. A person who speaks the same language have its own grammar. People who speak the same language are able to communicate because they intuitively know the grammar system of that language-that is, the rules of making meaning. Students who are native speakers of English words, the meanings of those words, and the different ways of putting words together make meaningful sentences.

English Language Mastery

Studies have shown that there is a strong correlation between people abilities with words and range of vocabulary and with success in their choosen field. People who can express themselves clearly are perceived as more intelligent and of higher status. They are accorded greater respect (www.destination-innovation.com/develop-your-greatest-skill-mastery-of-language).

Call centers focus on individuals from many regions within the different English speaking countries. Learning English, the hard part, is already done. But any person with some ESL training can learn the language well enough to communicate. English is a difficult language to learn and people speak differently. Working to master how different native speakers use the language can also prove exciting and challenging ([http://www.callcenteresl.com/mastering-english-understanding-the -costumers-need-as-a-csr](http://www.callcenteresl.com/mastering-english-understanding-the-costumers-need-as-a-csr)).

Mastery in sentence construction, regardless of the country or the language is the foundation for communication. When a message is relayed with the correct grammar it is easier to understand the purpose and meaning of that message. Applying grammar rules in daily communications can help learners develop the habit of printing logically and clearly and the speaker are able to become more accurate when using the language (www.witlanguageschool.com).

Views of Pronunciation

In the field of English as a second language (ESL) the necessity for, and method of, teaching pronunciation has become a controversial topic. Many second language educators have varied opinions on the importance practice within their lesson plans.

The process of learning English is interconnected. This means that each area of the language that is being taught helps improve other aspects of the language.

O’Malley and Chamot (1990)define learning strategies as “special thoughts or behaviors that individuals use to help them comprehend, lean, or retain new information” and classify these strategies into three major types: metacognitive strategies, cognitive strategies, cognitive strategies, and social or affective strategies.

Oxford (1990), points that in learning strategies the learnerscompile most comprehensive classification of language learning strategies.

Oxford (1990) distinguishes between direct ILS, “which do not directly involve the subject matter itself, but are essential to language learning nonetheless”. One point to note about the learning strategies is that they “are not the preserve of highly capable individuals, but could be learned by others who had not discovered them on their own” (O’Malley &Chamot 1990).

Gilbert (1994), claims that pronunciation has been something of an orphan in English programs around the world. Why has

pronunciation been a poor relation? I think it is because the subject has been drilled to death, with too few results from too much effort.

Most of the literature on pronunciation deals with what and how to teach, while the learner remains a silent abstract in the classroom. Morley (1994) underlies that the prevalent focus on pronunciation teaching nowadays should be on designing new wave instructional programs. Moreover, Morley stresses that these instructional designs should take into account not only language forms and functions, but also issues of learner self-involvement and learner strategy training. In other words, students who have develop the skills to monitor and modify their speech patterns if necessary should become active partners in their own learning. Yule et al (1987) assert that self-monitoring is critical for creating independent and competent learners and is a necessary part of the consciousness raising process.

Kriedler (1989), states that the correct and clear pronunciation are considerably important in language learning. Without them, learners may not be understood and may be poorly perceived by the English speakers. They need to have confidence in their ability to speak. Good pronunciation takes time to build up, as there are many factors involved.

Pronunciation is a very important factor in the speech process when the speaker achieves the goal to communicate effectively by being understood. The speech process is a process that involves several stages, beginning with the speaker's ideas and ending with the understanding of those ideas by the listener, Dauer (1993).

Dauer (1993), states that the speaker thinks decides what he or she going to say and puts the ideas into words and sentences of a particular language. The speaker's brain transforms the words and sentences into nerve impulses that it sends to the muscles in the speech organs where the speaker's speech organs move.

Suter (1976) and Suter and Purcell (1980) conclude that pronunciation practice in class had little effect on the learner's pronunciation skills. The attainment of accurate pronunciation in a second language is a matter substantially beyond the control of educators. They qualified their findings by stating the variables of formal training and the quality of the training in pronunciation could affect the results, as would the area of pronunciation that had been emphasized, the segmental and supra segmental patterns.

Jones (1994) found that students with prior exposure to phonological rules and principles, although they do not always produce more accurate pronunciation, seem to be better equipped to assess their own speech and to be more aware of their particular problems.

Morley (1991) states that the goal of pronunciation should be changed from the attainment to be more realistic goals of developing functional intelligibility, communicability, increased self- confidence, the development of speech monitoring abilities and speech modification strategies for use beyond the classroom.

Abercrombie (1991) defines comfortable intelligibility as pronunciation which can be understood with little or no conscious effort on the part of listener. Abercrombie (1991), also states being an intelligible speaker is to understand and to be understood. There are many English training courses teaching speaking but they do not focus on pronunciation.

Morley (1991) also states that the overall aim is for the learner to develop spoken English that is easy to understand, serves the learner's individual needs, and allows a positive image as a speaker of a foreign language.

O'Niel (2000), defined through the use of Total Learning environment Assessment (TLEA), developed for a prior study Texas private schools. It is an instrument that rates facility conditions on such factors as educational adequacy, environment for education, space flexibility, and cosmetic condition.

Yong (2004), defined pronunciation is the foundation of speaking. English both written and spoken, has been accepted as the dominant means of communication for most of the world but some misunderstandings have been caused by inappropriate pronunciation.

Fraser (2000), states poor communication can condemn learners to less social, academic and work advancement than they deserved.

Dan (2006), also states good pronunciation may make the communication easier and more relaxed and thus more successful. Almost all learners rate pronunciation as a priority and an area in which they need more guidance.

Wongsothorn, Sukakamolun&Chinthammit (1996), A national survey of English use revealed English being used to communicate with native speakers and non-native speakers from countries such as Japan and Germany as an international language and that English is generally taught by Thai teachers in schools and in higher education.

Wongbiasaj (2003), surveys in one Thai university of learner needs, Baker (2003) showed that Thai learners wanted to communicate with English native speakers and the further surveys of Timmis (2002) showed their desire to speak English. In response to this it has been recommended that teachers aid learners to become aware of the accent like an English native speaker.

Christiane Dalton and Barbara Seidlhofer (1995), stated that pronunciation in general terms as the production of significant sound in two senses. The first sense is talk about pronunciation as the production and reception of sound speech. Then the second is talk about pronunciation with reference to acts of speaking. In the simple word, we can define pronunciation as a part of speaking skill that related with how to make correct sounds in order to achieve meaning in context of use.

Kiedler (1989), states that correct and clear pronunciation are considerably important in language learning. Without them, learners may not be understood and maybe poorly perceived by the other English speakers.

Seidlhofer (1995) as cited by Balabagan (2015) states that pronunciation is never an end in itself but a means of negotiating meaning in discourse, embedded in specific socio cultural and interpersonal contexts.

Views in Vocabulary

Vocabulary as defined in Meriam-Webster dictionary, are all words known and used by a particular person. Knowing a word, however, is not as simple as simply being able to recognize it or used it. There are several aspects of word knowledge which are used to measure world knowledge.

Steven Stahl (2005) puts it, “Vocabulary knowledge is knowledge; the knowledge of a word not only implies a definition, but also implies how that word fits into the world”. Vocabulary knowledge is not something that expands and deepens over the course of a lifetime. Instruction in vocabulary involves far more than looking up words in a dictionary and using the words in a sentence. Vocabulary is acquired incidentally through explicit words and word-learning strategies.

Beardwell and Hidden (1994) consider training and development as a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behaviour through learning experiences to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities.

Reading Rockets (2005), vocabulary knowledge is not something that can ever be fully mastered. It is something that expands and depends over the course of a lifetime. Instruction in vocabulary involves far more than looking upwards in a dictionary and using the words in a sentence. Vocabulary is acquired incidentally through indirect exposure towards in intentionally through explicit instruction in specific words, and word-learning strategies (www.readingrockets.org/artcle/teaching-vocabulary).

Fluency in the Call Center

Dictionary defines fluency as “the ability to speak easily and smoothly and the ability to do something in a way that seems very easy. For true fluency, there is an assumption of unconscious effort, as if the action or the words come easily. But as just as there is tremendous effort in learning a new language, there is significant effort in taking on any new skill and practicing it enough until it becomes unconscious or seemingly easy.

This “practice makes perfect” strategy applies to call center training as well. There are some skills that will be difficult to learn and perfect, while others are learned easily but still need to be repeated over and over in order to become automatic behaviours. Getting to the last phrase of unconscious competence or fluency involves defining the behaviour, training for it, and then the agent becomes comfortable with the words and process and can instead devote mindshare to listening and focusing on customer needs one-on-one to enhance service or the sale (<http://www.qatc.org/winter-2016-connection/training-for-fluency-in-the-call-center>).

Aicart (2016) defines native speaker that one who have learned their first language as children., while fluent speakers are the ones who have learned their second language after infancy and who as a combination of their motivation, hard work. As children we acquire the language in an organic way thanks to the implication of the limbic system and our sub cortical areas (Lieberman, 2000; Petitto, 2009).

A call center agent, talk to native speaker all over the world. They need to be able to understand a native English speakers’ accent with no problem. Thus, call center representative needs to communicate as native speakers, in short, they need to understand English (<https://pisopinoy.com/work-ina-call-center/>).

Filipino call center agents speak without any hint of an accent. This seemingly small detail player a big role in the conversational quality between an agent and the caller. Accent can make it harder for the caller to understand what the agent is saying, and this make for an unpleasant customer service experience. The Filipino’s accent-neutral or accent-free speech is one of the qualities that make them a preferred call center agents of westerns (<http://www.magellan-solutions.com/blog/offshore-outsoucring-how-the-English-communication-skills-of-Filipino>).

Good communication improves the development of fluency. When a person has learned to speak the language more accurately, it will be easier for the person to know how to organize and express the ideas in their mind without difficulty. As a result, they will be able speak, read and write the language more fluently. When a person immerse to a native speaker his volubility and eloquency or a system that delivers information quickly become expertise. In other words, fluency is achieved when one can access knowledge and produce language unconsciously and automatically (www.witlanguageschool.com).

Language Proficiency

Language is the thought of people and people have their own language as they have their own way of feeling (Rizal,1891). It is man’s oldest, and some as the greatest invention for society (Cruz, 2013)

Andrews (2001) expectations, belief and views about the oral language proficiency of language teachers, especially of non-native language teachers and more extensively with reference to contexts of EFL, have been dealt with in a number of articles and studies in the areas of foreign language learning and teaching language testing and the teacher education.

Hujailan (2004), has evaluated English language proficiency of college students in 18 college in Saudi Arabia with focus on the main language skills. He found out that college students have low level of proficiency in all four language skills, especially in writing. His

study concluded that there is an immediate need for remedial programmes sided by an overall review of all teaching and learning processes at the teacher's colleges.

In addition, language proficiency is the ability of the individual to speak or perform in an acquired language. As theories vary among pedagogues as to what constituents' proficiency, there is little consistency as to how different organizations classify it. Additionally, fluency and language competence are generally recognized as being related, but separate controversial subjects.

Oral Language Proficiency

There are also contentions from various experts regarding oral proficiency. One of them is Silva (1990), who points out the oral proficiency contributes for a review of what "fluency" means as a descriptor of OLP, stands in a large scope of linguistic aspects involved in spoken language (Lennon, 1990), it is also interpreted as a synonym for the overall competence in speaking skills required or desirable for ELF teachers.

Johnston (2006) confirms the above ideas by saying that the presentation of new words is only the first step in the process of language learning. He adds that motivation is a strong factor in all the aspects of learning the language. Through this, the students themselves are interested in learning specific words or phrases encountered in any reading material available at hand.

Parcon (2012), reveals that the students' degree success is based on their proficiency in English. Many look at one's competence and performance in English as indicator of readiness and adaptability to college work (Bloom, 1987). College students on the other hand are expected to have advanced English proficiency considering their many years of exposure to the English Language, both in written and oral discourse to cope with the demands of the present time.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive-survey method is used in this study. It is the most appropriate design applicable in determining the Oral English adaptation before and during their employment of the BSEd-English graduates and who will work as call center agents. Since the present condition is concerned with the BSEd-English call center agents' Oral Proficiency in terms of Grammar, Sentence Mastery, Fluency, Vocabulary and Pronunciation, the data that will be gathered using the descriptive-survey method wherein the responses will be tabulated, analyzed and interpreted through the use of statistical measures.

Respondents

The subjects of the study were the fifteen (15) BSEd-English Graduates from random public and private schools who worked as Call Center Agents for the school year of 2023-2024. The subjects of the study had taken the English Proficiency Test and TOEFL test for Teachers.

Instrument

The researchers utilized the English Proficiency Test and TOEFL test for teacher as instruments in the gathering the data which contain items adapted and modified from various English proficiency test and TOEFL test for teachers' which suit to the level of the teachers. Test of English as a Foreign Language known as TOEFL test is a standardized test to measure the English Language ability of non-native speakers to evaluate the English speaking and understanding ability of a speaker.

The researchers patterned her 15 item grammar test from TOEFL Test. The next research instrument is adapted from Language Skills Institute (LSI) which is used by TESDA to measure the teachers' knowledge on pronunciation, sentence mastery and vocabulary. These English Proficiency tests contain 15 items for both sentence mastery and vocabulary. This test has been utilized in TESDA to measure the teachers' English Proficiency. Considering that the test has been tried out in many groups of teachers, its validity has been established.

In addition, the next test for pronunciation and retelling is adapted from Parcon (2012). It is a reading aloud activity where the teachers' pronunciation was described as excellent, very good, good, margined, limited, and intermittent. These utilized a rubric which that determined the teacher's pronunciation level English through reading aloud activity.

Procedure

After the approval of the research proposal by the panelist, the researchers administered an English Proficiency Test to all BSEd-English graduates school year (2018-2019) who worked as call center agents in (2022-2023). After which, the researchers will orient the subjects of the study about the nature of the test.

After the orientation, the English Proficiency Tests was administered to the subjects. After the completion of the test, the test papers were retrieved and checked.

The data will be tallied, analyzed, and interpreted. After two (2) months of their employment in the call center, the same test was administered to the BSEd-English graduates. The results of the test before their employment and during their employment as call center

agents were correlated. Then the data were analyzed and interpreted as basis for the summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations.

Data Analysis

The researcher used the descriptive statistic particularly the frequency counts, percentage and description in answering problems 1 and 2. In answering the problem 3 the t-test set at 0.05 level of significant was used.

Results and Discussion

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates in Terms of Grammar before they become Call Center Agents.

The frequency, percentage and description distribution of The English Proficiency level of BSEd – English Call Center Agents in terms of Grammar is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Grammar*

Range of Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
13 – 15	8	53.33	Very Good
10 – 12	4	26.67	Good
7 – 9	2	13.33	Average
4 – 6	1	6.67	Poor
1 – 3	0	0	Very Poor
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 11.80 (Good)			

The English Proficiency test is given to BSED-Graduates Before and during their employment as call center agents to measure their English Proficiency Level in grammar the result of the test showed that out of 15 BSEd-English Graduates, 8 or 53.33 percent has obtained scores ranging from 13-15 described as very good. This means that little more than half of the BSEd-English Graduates are excellent in grammar. This means that the respondents have correctly given the correct answer when asked to identify the errors in the sentence. This implies that they mastered the basic rules of grammar even before their employment as call center agents.

The Table also shows that out of 15, 4 or 26.67 percent obtained scores ranging from 10-12 with the description of Good. This indicates that one-third of BSEd-English Graduates' has high level of proficiency in grammar. Likewise only 2 or 13.33 percent has got the score in the range of 7-9 described as average. Meaning, only 2 of BSEd-English graduates have shown minimum competency in grammar. The data suggest that they need to master the basic grammar rules so that they can easily spot grammar errors. This further reveals that they can spot the grammar errors easily in the given sentences.

Furthermore, only 1 or 6.67 percent has obtained the score in the score range of 4-6 described as poor. This means that before the employment of the BSEd-English Graduates as call center agents 1 of them got very low in the grammar test. This shows that the said respondent does not meet internalize basic grammar rules that guide him in spotting the errors in the given sentences. Likewise, none got the score in the range of 1-3 described as very poor.

In totality, the respondents' mean score in grammar is 11.80 described as Good. It explains that even prior to the employment of the BSEd-English Graduates to Call Centers, they also possess enough knowledge in grammar rules that aided them in answering the grammar test. It can be attributed to substantial inputs about grammar lesson.

In support to the above data, Carolyn (1998) argues that before the learners engage in speaking comprehension of spoken language must be developed. This method was based on the idea that speaking in the target language emerge naturally hence there is no point in forcing them to speak before they are ready. The learners are expected to understand the grammar rules naturally without explanations, the way grammar is taught in total physical response has been questioned.

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates in Terms of Sentence Mastery before they become Call Center Agents.

The English Proficiency Level in Sentence Mastery of the BSEd-English Graduates before their Employment as call center is presented in Table 2. The data on Table 2 is presented on the succeeding page.

Before the employment of 15 BSEd-English Graduates in the call centers, they were given sentence mastery test. The result shows that out 15 respondents, 10 or 66.67 percent has obtained the score in the range of 13-15 described as very good.

This means that majority of the respondents got very high scores when asked to arrange words or phrases to form a correct sentence. It implies that even before the employment of the BSEd-English Graduates to call centers, they are already knowledgeable about sentence construction. It can be attributed to the substantial inputs they received from the different courses they took in college.

Table 2. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Sentence Mastery*

Range of Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
13 – 15	10	66.67	Very Good
10 – 12	1	6.67	Good
7 – 9	2	13.33	Average
4 – 6	2	13.33	Poor
1 – 3	0	0	Very Poor
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 11.80 (Good)			

In addition, 2 or 13.33 percent got the score in the score range of 7-9 described as average. This means that only very few of the respondents possess minimum competency in arranging the word or phrase to construct correct sentences. This suggest that these respondents still need additional inputs on grammar rules and vocabulary to successfully arrange words and phrase to construct correct sentences.

Likewise, 2 or 13.33 percent got the score in the range of 4-6 labeled as poor. This means that before the respondents' employment to call centers, they were 2 of them who have difficulty in arranging words or phrases to construct correct sentences. This tells that 2 of respondents have difficulty in arranging correct sentences. This can be attributed about sentence construction.

In totality, Table 2 reflects a mean score of 11. 80 described as good. It reveals that when all the scores of the students' mastery are considered the result in good. This means that the respondents high level of competence in sentence mastery even before their employment in call centers. This means that they have enough background on how to coin words and phrases to form sentences. Studies have shown that there is a strong correlation between people abilities with words and range of vocabulary and with success in their chosen field. People who can express themselves clearly are perceived as more intelligent and of higher status. They are accorded greater respect (www.destination-innovation.com/develop-your-greatest-skill-mastery-of-language).

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates in Terms of Vocabulary before they become Call Center Agents.

The English Proficiency Level in Vocabulary of the BSEd-English Graduates before their employment as call center agents is presented in Table 3. Data on Table 3 is presented on the succeeding page.

Table 3 presents the English Proficiency Level of the respondents in vocabulary before their employment as call center agents. It can be seen in Table 3 that there are 8 or 53.33 percent of the respondents who got the score within the range of 13-15 labeled as very good. The data disclose that more than one half of the respondents can give the meaning of the phrases correctly. This manifests that they possess good background in word meaning, and they have enough stock of vocabulary.

Table 3. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Vocabulary*

Range of Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
13 – 15	8	53.33	Very Good
10 – 12	2	13.33	Good
7 – 9	3	20.00	Average
4 – 6	2	13.33	Poor
1 – 3	0	0	Very Poor
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 11.20 (Good)			

Moreover, 3 or 20 percent of the respondents have obtained the score in the range of 7-9 labeled as average. The result is an indication that there are few respondents only possess minimum competency in giving the correct meaning of the given phrases. With this, they still need additional inputs on Vocabulary.

Additionally, 2 or 13.33 percent falls on the score range of 10-12 described as good and 4-6 described as poor. This connotes that only 2 respondents have high level of competence in vocabulary. This means that they have enough learned more vocabularies which guided them in giving the correct meaning of phrases. In contrast, there are also 2 of the respondents who are poor in vocabulary. This means that they have enough learned more vocabularies which guide them in giving the correct meaning of phrases. In contrast, there are also 2 of the respondents who are poor in vocabulary. They do not have enough background on vocabulary building, and need reinforcement in this area.

In general, Table 3 shows a mean score of 11.20 described as good. This means that the respondents knowledgeable in giving the correct

meaning of the given phrases. The result indicates that even before the employment of the respondents as call center agents, they already possess high level of competence in terms of vocabulary. It can be attributed enough training through sound instruction regarding vocabulary development. Vocabulary is the knowledge of words and word meanings. As Steven Stahl (2005) puts it, "Vocabulary knowledge is knowledge; the knowledge of a word not only implies a definition, but also implies how that word fits into the world". Vocabulary knowledge is not something that expands and deepens over the course of a lifetime. Instruction in vocabulary involves far more than looking up words in a dictionary and using the words in a sentence. Vocabulary is acquired incidentally through explicit words and word-learning strategies. According to Michael Graves (2000), there are four components of an effective vocabulary program.

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates in Terms of Pronunciation before they become Call Center Agents.

The BSEd-English graduates were given pronunciation test before they become call center agents. The result is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Pronunciation

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
6	4	26.67	Excellent
5	7	46.67	Very Good
4	3	20.00	Good
3	1	6.67	Marginal
2	0	0	Limited
1	0	0	Intermittent
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 4.93 (Very Good)			

Table 4 reflects the English Proficiency Level of the BSEd-English Graduates particularly in pronunciation before their employment as call center agents. It can be gleaned in Table 4 that out of 15, 7 or 46.67 percent of the respondents have scored 5 as very good in the pronunciation test. This means that the students have no conspicuous pronunciation when asked to read the selection aloud. However, their pronunciation skill can't be taken for native speaker.

Moreover, 4 or 26.67 percent of the BSEd-English Graduates got the score of 6 described as excellent. This means that little more than one fourth of the students have shown a native like pronunciation in a read aloud activity. It further means that in reading aloud activity, there are BSEd- English Graduates who can approximate the pronunciation of native speakers. These results can be attributed to their trainings and exposure to English Language. There are BSEd-English Graduates who graduated from private schools which provide adequate trainings on Oral English Proficiency. There are schools also are equipped with facilities that complement students Oral Proficiency. Thus, they demonstrate high level of competence in Oral English. Studies are increasing their focus on the impact that the environment design will have on student outcomes.

When the learning process is at the core of design priorities, there is a significant likelihood that the facility will positively influence performance (Blair, 1998). More profoundly, O'Neil (2000), defined through the use of Total Learning environment Assessment (TLEA), developed for a prior study Texas private schools. It is an instrument that rates facility conditions on such factors as educational adequacy, environment for education, space flexibility, and cosmetic condition.

The same table reflects that out of 15 respondents 3 or 20 percent has obtained a score of 4 described as good. This means that few of the students have intelligible utterances while reading the selection aloud, but their speech is occasionally hesitant with some unevenness caused by rephrasing and grouping of words. The data suggest that the students need more practice in using the target language in a communicative situation.

Out of 15 respondents, only 1 or 6.67 percent of the students has obtained the score of 3 described as Marginal. This means that only 1 out of 15 students has shown observable errors in pronouncing English words while reading the selection aloud. This implies that only 1 out of 15 is in need of rigid practice on the correct production of English sounds to read the selection aloud with accuracy.

This contradicts with the idea stated by Yong (2004) that pronunciation is the foundation of speaking. English both written and spoken, has been accepted as the dominant means of communication for most of the world but some misunderstandings have been caused by inappropriate pronunciation. Poor communication can condemn learners to less social, academic and work advancement than they deserved (Fraser, 2000). Good pronunciation may make the communication easier and more relaxed and thus more successful (Dan, 2006).

Furthermore, data in Table 4 clearly state that none of the students has demonstrated low and very low scores in the read aloud activity. This explains that the students' utterances are still intelligible. Their utterances do not display errors with very heavy accent that make understanding very difficult and their utterances do not show unintelligibility that causes misconceptions.

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates in Terms of Fluency before they become Call Center Agents.

The English Proficiency of the students particularly their fluency is determined through fluency test. The result is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Fluency*

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
6	2	13.33	Excellent
5	5	33.33	Very Good
4	7	46.67	Good
3	1	6.67	Marginal
2	0	0	Limited
1	0	0	Intermittent
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 4.53 (Very Good)			

Data in Table 5 reflect the students' fluency scores. Out of 15 students 7 or 46.67 percent got the score of 4 with the description of good. This means that nearly one half of the students have shown ease and speed of the flow of speech, but their utterances have displayed occasional hesitation with some unevenness caused by rephrasing and grouping of words. This further explains that these students did not achieve perfection in terms of fluency.

Table 5 also reveals that 5 or 33.33 percent got the score of 5 or 33.33 percent got the score of 5 described as very good. This means that there are few students whose speech is effortless and smooth but perceptibly non-native in speech and unevenness.

In the highest level there are 2 or 13.33 percent has garnered the score of 6 described as excellent. The data tell the students' speech in retelling the anecdote including the setting, characters, and events is as effortless and smooth as native speakers. This means that there are 2 students whose utterances in retelling an anecdote have achieved highest degree of ease and precision as reflected in their utterances.

Moreover, out of 15 respondents 1 or 6.67 percent got the score of 3. This means that only 1 student is observed to have frequent hesitation, jerky, and incomplete sentences.

Among the respondents, none of them is described as limited and intermittent speaker, for no one got the score the score of 2 and 1.

In totality, students' mean score in fluency in 4.53 described as very good. The data reveal that generally the speech of the students is effortless and smooth but perceptibly non-native in speed and unevenness.

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates During Their Employment as Call Center Agents in Terms of Grammar

During the employment of BSEd-English graduates as call center agents, the English proficiency level of the students in grammar is determined through a grammar test. The result is reflected in Table 6.

Table 6. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Grammar*

Range of Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
13 – 15	9	60.00	Very Good
10 – 12	3	20.00	Good
7 – 9	3	20.00	Average
4 – 6	0	0	Poor
1 – 3	0	0	Very Poor
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 13.25 (Very Good)			

The result of the grammar test shows that during the employment of BSEd-English Graduates as call center agents, there are 9 or 60.00 percent out of 15 respondents got scores in the range of 13-15 categorized as very good. This means that majority of the students have given correct answers with only minimal errors in finding out the errors in the sentences. This reveals that the students' have internalized the different grammar rules that help them give a correct answer to every item.

In the same table, 3 or 20 percent has garnered the score in score range of 10-12 described as good. This means that few of the students have garnered high score when asked to find out errors in the sentence. It indicates that the students are familiar about the grammar rules, and they know how to apply these rules in writing.

Another 3 or 20 percent of the students got the score range of 7-9 described as average. This means that few of the students possess minimum competency in finding out the errors in the given sentences. This means that the students have only obtained passing score when asked to find out the errors in the sentences. The result of the study reveals that the students need more knowledge about grammar rules so that they can spot the given sentences.

Finally, no one obtained the range of 4-6 labeled as poor and 1-3 labeled as very poor. The data show that none of the students got low and very low in the grammar test.

In totality, the students got a mean score of 13.15 described as very good in the grammar test. The data disclose that the students are familiar of the different grammar rules that guide team in finding out the errors in the sentences.

The English Level of BSEd – English Graduates During Their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Sentence Mastery

During the Employment of BSEd-English Graduates as call center agents, their oral English proficiency level in sentence mastery is measured through a test.

The frequency, percentage, and description of oral English proficiency level of BSEd-English Graduates in Sentence Mastery is revealed in Table 7.

Table 7. Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Sentence Mastery

Range of Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
13 – 15	12	80.00	Very Good
10 – 12	1	6.67	Good
7 – 9	1	6.67	Average
4 – 6	1	6.67	Poor
1 – 3	0	0	Very Poor
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 12.80 (Very Good)			

Table 7 shows that out of 15 respondents 12 or 80 percent got the score range of 13-15 categorized as very good. This shows that during the employment of the BSEd-English Graduates as call center agents, majority of them can correctly arrange words and phrases to construct correct sentences. This means that they are knowledgeable in joining words together to form a correct sentence, for they obtained a very high score in completing this task.

In addition only 1 or 6.67 percent has obtained the score in the score range of 7-9 described average and 1 or 6.67 percent obtained the score range of 4-6 described poor and none obtained the score of very poor. The data disclose that all of the students are very competent in arranging words and phrase to form a correct sentence, for only very few of the students got the scores which description is good average and poor.

Generally, the mean score of the students in sentence mastery test is 12.80 labeled as very good. It divulger that the students do not find difficulty in arranging words or phrases to form grammatical sentences. This explains that the BSEd-English Graduates have enough background in the different rules of grammar which aided them in constructing grammatical sentences.

In line with this, cited by Balabagan (2015), one area of writing that may be particularly problematic for less skilled writers and language learners is constructing well-formed sentences (Saddler, 2008). As stated by Chin (2000), grammar is the sound, structure, and meaning system of language. All languages have grammar, and each language has its own grammar. A person who speaks the same language have its own grammar. People who speak the same language are able to communicate because they intuitively know the grammar system of that language-that is, the rules of making meaning. Students who are native speakers of English words, the meanings of those words, and the different ways of putting words together make meaningful sentences.

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates During Their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Vocabulary

The frequency, percentage and description distribution of The English Proficiency level of BSEd – English Call Center Agents in terms of Vocabulary is exhibited in Table 8.

In terms of vocabulary, Table 8 show that out of 15 respondents 13 or 86.66 percent got the score in the score range of 13-15 classified as very good. This means that almost all of the students have correctly given the correct word that best describes each given phrase. This is shown in their scores in the vocabulary test. The data imply that the students have understood the meaning of the given phrase, for they have spotted the correct answer. Considering their scores in vocabulary which is very high, this further reveals that the respondents have through background about vocabulary, and received enough inputs about vocabulary building. Probably, it is due to their orientation, for they graduated major in English.

Table 8. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Vocabulary*

Range of Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
13 – 15	13	86.66	Very Good
10 – 12	1	6.67	Good
7 – 9	1	6.67	Average
4 – 6	0	0	Poor
1 – 3	0	0	Very Poor
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 13.40 (Very Good)			

In addition, only 1 or 6.67 percent got the score in the range of 10-12 described as good, and where is also another 1 or 6.67 percent who got the score in the range of 7-9 described as average. In the score range of poor and very poor no one got the score that falls on this score description. The data further imply that during the BSEd-English Graduates employment as call center agents they have shown expertise in answering the vocabulary test especially when asked to select the correct word that best describes the phrase. This score manifest their good background in comprehension and vocabulary for almost of them got very high score in vocabulary and only few of them have gotten the scores that fall on the good and average. Fortunately, none of them have gotten the score with the description of poor and very poor.

Considering all the cores of the respondents in the vocabulary test, Table 8 reflects the mean score of 13.40 labeled as very good. This is an indication that during the respondents' employment as call center agents, they have shown very high level of competence in terms of giving the correct word that best describes a phrase. Their commendable scores in vocabulary can be attributed to their trainings as BSEd-English Graduates and their exposure to the use of English Language in their work of behaviour through learning, which occurs as a result of education, instructions and development and planned experience. Training is the process of equipping the workforce with the necessary knowledge, skills and attitude to tackle the job responsibilities. Staff development on the other hand is improvement of the employees' competences for future environmental demands and adaptability.

Thus, Beardwell and Hidden (1994) consider training and development as a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behaviour through learning experiences to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities.

English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates During Their Employment as Call Center Agents in Terms of Pronunciation

Table 9 presents the English Proficiency Level in Pronunciation of BSEd-English graduates during their employment as call center agents. The data include range of score, frequency, percentage, and description. The data on Table 9 is presented in succeeding page.

In terms of pronunciation of the BSEd-English Graduates during their employment as call center agents, the data in Table 9 show that out of 15 respondents 8 or 53.33 percent have obtained the perfect score of 6. This means that these respondents have articulated the English words with native like pronunciation during the reading aloud activity.

Table 9. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of Oral English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Pronunciation*

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
6	8	53.33	Excellent
5	6	40.00	Very Good
4	1	6.67	Good
3	0	0	Marginal
2	0	0	Limited
1	0	0	Intermittent
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 5.40 (Very Good)			

This further reveals that more than one half of the respondents can approximate the pronunciation of the native English speakers as they do their work as call center agents. Being an intelligible speaker is to understand and to be understood (Abercrombie, 1991). There are many English training courses teaching speaking but they do not focus on pronunciation. As English teaching has moved to language functions and communicative competencies, a new urgency for the teaching of pronunciation has arisen (Celce-Murcia, 1987; Morley, 1994; Gilbert, 1994).

Furthermore, A national survey of English use revealed English being used to communicate with native speakers and non-native speakers from countries such as Japan and Germany as an international language and that English is generally taught by Thai teachers

in schools and in higher education (Wongsothorn, Sukakamolsun&Chinthammit, 1996). From surveys in one Thai university of learner needs, Baker (2003) showed that Thai learners wanted to communicate with English native speakers and the further surveys of Timmis (2002) showed their desire to speak English. In response to this it has been recommended that teachers aid learners to become aware of the accent like an English native speaker (Wongbiasaj, 2003).

Moreover, 6 or 40 percent have obtained the score of 5 described as very good. This means more than one third of the respondents have articulated the English words, phrases, and sentences during the reading aloud activity with no conspicuous pronunciation, but their sound production would not taken for native speakers. This means that the respondents have pronounced the English words in the English text correctly but their pronunciation did not use the marker of native speakers of English language. However, their pronunciation is still understandable at a global level.

In addition, 1 or 6.67 percent got the score of good. This means that though the speaker has successfully read the text aloud, they have shown occasional errors and mispronunciation. This means that the respondents needs further training in this aspect.

In contrary, none got the score of 3,2, and 1 with the descriptions of Marginal, Limited, and Intermittent. This is an indication that the pronunciation of BSEd-English Graduates who are employed as call center agents is intelligent and unusually accepted.

In totality, Table 9 has a mean score of 5.40 described as very good. The data show that the BSEd-English call center agents have very good pronunciation skill. They can produce the English sound correctly and intelligibly. Pronunciation is an essential part of speaking (oral communication). It involves making correct sounds of a particular language, as well as how the sounds are put together in the flow of speech (not just in isolated words). A necessary part of intelligible pronunciation in English also involves knowing how to stress words correctly and how to use intonation appropriately.

Moreover, based on Christiane Dalton and Barbara Seidlhofer (2017) in Pronunciation book, they stated that pronunciation in general terms as the production of significant sound in two senses. The first sense is talk about pronunciation as the production and reception of sound speech. Then the second is talk about pronunciation with reference to acts of speaking. In the simple word, we can define pronunciation as a part of speaking skill that related with how to make correct sounds in order to achieve meaning in context of use.

English Proficiency Level in Fluency of BSEd – English Graduates During Their Employment as Call Center Agents

The fluency level of BSEd-English Graduates during their employment as call center agents is shown in Table 10.

Table 10. *Frequency, Percentage and Description Distribution of Oral English Proficiency Level of BSEd – English Graduates Before their Employment as Call Center Agents in terms of Fluency*

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
6	7	46.67	Excellent
5	7	46.67	Very Good
4	1	6.67	Good
3	0	0	Marginal
2	0	0	Limited
1	0	0	Intermittent
Total	15	100.00	
Mean = 5.40 (Very Good)			

Data in Table 10 revealed that out of 15 respondents 7 or 46.67 percent got the score of 6 classified as excellent in the in the fluency test. This means that almost one half of the BSEd-English graduates who are call center agents have successfully retold the anecdote including the setting, characters and events in an effortless and smooth manner like the nature speakers. Probably, they have unconsciously acquired the accent of the nature speakers during their interactive transaction through computers or phone as part of their work as call center agent.

A call center agent, talk to native speaker all over the world. They need to be able to understand a native English speakers' accent with no problem. Thus, call center representative needs to communicate as native speakers, in short, they need to understand English(<https://pisopinoy.com/work-ina-call-center/>). Compared to fellow Asian forerunners, Filipino call center agents speak without any hint of an accent. This seemingly small detail player a big role in the conversational quality between an agent and the caller. Accent can make it harder for the caller to understand what the agent in saying, and this make for an unpleasant customer service experience. The Filipino's accent-neutral or accent-free speech is one of the qualities that make them a preferred call center agents of westerns (<http://www.magellan-solutions.com/blog/offshore-outsoucring-how-the-English-communication-skills-of-Filipino>).

Additionally, Table 10 also reflects that out of 15 respondents, 7 or 46.67 percent got the score of 5 described as very good in the fluency test. This means that almost fifty percent of the students have effortless and smooth but perceptibly non-native in speed and evenness in their speech when asked to retell the anecdote.It further unveils that less than 50 percent of the respondents have clear and intelligible utterances when asked to retell the anecdote, but then speed does not manifest American accent. Nevertheless that perceptibly non-native speed and unevenness in their speech, they are understood globally.

Likewise, Table 10 also uncovers that only 1 or 6.67 percent of the BSED-English call center agents got the score of 4 labeled as good in the fluency test. The data delineate that there is only 1 of 15 respondents whose speech is occasionally hesitant with some unevenness caused by rephrasing and grouping of words.

In the scores of 3, 2, and 1 labeled as Marginal, Limited, and Intermittent, None of the BSEd-English Graduates who are call center agents have obtained these scores. The data uncover that none of the call center agents has frequent hesitant and jerky speech and sentences which are left incomplete. In addition, there is no speech which is very slow and uneven except for too short sentences or routine sentences. It also reveals that none of the call center agents has halting and fragmentary speech when asked to retell the anecdote.

In consequence, Table 10 has a mean score of 5.40 labeled as very good. This disclosed that the BSED-English Graduates who are call center agents have effortless and smoother speech when asked to retell an anecdote. This shows that they are very fluent in speaking using the English language.

Comparison of the BSED- English Graduates English Proficiency level in the five (5) English parameter Before and During their Employment as Call Center Agents.

The English proficiency level of the BSED-English graduates in five (5) language areas are compared before and during their employment as call center agents. The result of the comparison is shown in Table 11.

Table 11. *Comparison of the BSEd Graduates' Oral English Proficiency Level Between Each of the five (5) Oral English Parameters Before and During their Employment as Call Center Agents*

Parameter	N	ΣD	ΣD2	Computed t-value
1. Grammar				
Before Employment as Call Center Agent	15	19	41	4.460
Significant				
During Employment as Call Center Agent				
2. Sentence Mastery				
Before Employment as Call Center Agent	15	14	26	4.365
Significant				
During Employment as Call Center Agent				
3. Vocabulary				
Before Employment as Call Center Agent	15	41	161	5.662
Significant				
During Employment as Call Center Agent				
4. Pronunciation				
Before Employment as Call Center Agent	15	9.35	8.95	5.112
Significant				
During Employment as Call Center Agent				
5. Fluency				
Before Employment as Call Center Agent	15	9.0	9.68	4.203
Significant				
During Employment as Call Center Agent				

Table 11 shows the comparison of the BSED-English graduates before and during their employment as call center agents. The difference between English Proficiency in grammar is gauged through t-test and the result is the t-value of 4.460 labeled as significant. This means that the BSED-English graduates' employment at call center has brought improvement in their grammar skill, Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the mean score in grammar before and during the employment of BSED-English graduates as call center agents is rejected.

Additionally, the sentence mastery of the respondents before and after employment at call center is also determined through sentence mastery. The t-test was used to find out the difference. It resulted to a computed t-value of 4.368 which is higher than the tabular value of ± 2.145. Thus, the difference is described as significant. This shows that the employment of the respondents in a call center has helped them improve their skill in sentence mastery. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the mean score in sentence mastery before and during the employment of BSED-English graduates as call center agents is rejected.

Thus, mastery in sentence construction, regardless of the country or the language is the foundation for communication. When a message is relayed with the correct grammar it is easier to understand the purpose and meaning of that message. Applying grammar rules in daily communications can help learners develop the habit of printing logically and clearly and the speaker are able to become more accurate when using the language (www.witlanguageschool.com).

Likewise, the vocabulary skill of the respondents was also compared using t-test. The result shows a computed t-value of 5.662 which is greater than the tabular value of ± 2.145 ; therefore, the difference is significant. This means that the respondents' vocabulary skill is improved by their employment to call center. This result can be attributed to the frequent use of English language by the respondents as they do their tasks as call center agents. Eventually, their frequent exposures to English language help them improve their vocabulary skill.

According to Reading Rockets (2005), vocabulary knowledge is not something that can ever be fully mastered. It is something that expands and depends over the course of a lifetime. Instruction in vocabulary involves far more than looking upwards in a dictionary and using the words in a sentence. Vocabulary is acquired incidentally through indirect exposure towards in intentionally through explicit instruction in specific words, and word-learning strategies (www.readingrockets.org/artcle/teaching-vocabulary).

On the other hand, the respondents' pronunciation skill before and during their employment as call center agents is also compared through t-test. The result is a computed t-value of 5.112 which is higher than the tabular value of ± 2.145 ; therefore, the t-value is described a significant.

This discloses that the pronunciation of the respondents is enhanced of their employment in the call center. Seidlhofer (as cited by Balabagan 2015)states that pronunciation is never an end in itself but a means of negotiating meaning in discourse, embedded in specific socio cultural and interpersonal contexts. Furthermore, pronunciation refers to the ability to use the correct stress, rhythm, and intonation of a word in a spoken language.

Dan (2016) states, good pronunciation make the communication easier and more relaxed and thus more successful. Almost all learners rate pronunciation as a priority and an area in which they need more guidance (Willing, 1993). In addition, Kiedler (1989) states that correct and clear pronunciation are considerably important in language learning. Without them, learners may not be understood and maybe poorly perceived by the other English speakers. Good pronunciation takes time to hear a lot of English before they can develop a feel for the sounds of English.

With this, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the mean score in pronunciation before and during their employment as call center agents is rejected.

Finally, Table 11 also reveals that the respondents' fluency before and during their employment as call center agents has significant difference as stated in the Computed t-value of 4.203 which is higher than the tabular value of ± 2.145 ; Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Good communication improves the development of fluency. When a person has learned to speak the language more accurately, it will be easier for the person to know how to organize and express the ideas in their mind without difficulty. As a result, they will be able speak, read and write the language more fluently. When a person immerse to a native speaker his volubility and eloquency or a system that delivers information quickly become expertise. In other words, fluency is achieved when one can access knowledge and produce language unconsciously and automatically (www.witlanguageschool.com).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the employment of BSEd-English graduate to call centers has positively contributed to the English adaptation of the respondents. Further, it is concluded that the employment of respondents to the call centers has improved their English proficiency level.

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following are recommended:

Recommend the use of the research output to teachers to use as enhancement activities of the students communication skills.

Higher Education Institutions offering Teachers Education may consider to continue providing substantial inputs and sound trainings to their students so that high level of English proficiency will be maintained.

Teachers handling English courses may provide exposure to their students to hear, to view, to listen, and to interact if possible with the native speakers of English to achieve higher level of English proficiency.

The BSEd-English graduates may explore all possibilities to have an avenue to be exposed with the utterances of the native speakers of English to further enhance their English proficiency.

Study similar to this can be conducted to other setting and respondents to further validate the results of the study.

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